

1. The stem-loop structure of Tnr2 element, 157 bp in length. Arrows indicate TSD of 8 bp.

Identifying transposonlike element Tnr2 in rice

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Tnr2 was found as an insertion sequence within p-SINE1-r4, a member of the retroposon p-SINE1, in rice. This sequence is 157 bp in length and present in multiple copies in the rice genome. Tnr2 has the 56-bp terminal inverted repeat sequence (TIR) and is flanked by an 8-bp direct repeat sequence. Tnr2 shows no homology with known transposable elements, suggesting that Tnr2 is a new transposable element (Fig. 1) (Mochizuki et al 1993, Ohtsubo et al 1993).

To analyze the inner region of Tnr2, we synthesized primers that hybridize the sequences of inverted repeats and carried out polymerase chain reaction (PCR) using genomic DNA of *Oryza sativa* L. cultivars IR36 (indica) and Nipponbare (japonica) as the template. The PCR-amplified fragments were cloned, and their nucleotide sequences determined. The Tnr2 members contained substitutions and deletions in their sequences. A consensus sequence derived from the nucleotide sequences of these members showed a 20-bp tandem repeat in the region between the TIR sequences (Fig. 2). A few members, however, had only one of the repeating sequences.

We identified three more Tnr2 members with flanking sequences by screening from the genomic library of IR36. Nucleotide sequencing of these members revealed that

Consensus	<u>CGGGACATTTAACTATTTTGGCCACTTTTAAGATGTGGCAATTA</u> <u>ACTATTTGGCCACTCGC/TGCTATGACATGTGGCCCT</u>	
pKAY410	aatatccg-----T-----A-----C-----T-----A-/-----A-A---	
D16-80	tagaaaag-----G-G-G-----A-A-----T-----/-----A-T---	
D11-89	gctggtgtG-----/---G-----C-----T-----A-----//-----T---	
H11-75	ctgcctccG-----AGGGA»	
	»A--A-----/-----A-C--GT-----G-----A-C-/---A-----	
pYK1	*****-----/-----C-----	
pYK2A	*****-----/---T-----A---	
pYK2B	*****-----A-/-----T-----A---	
pYK3	*****-----T-/-----A---	
pYK4	*****-----T-/---T-----A---	
pYK5	*****-----A-/-----T-----A---	
pYK6	*****-----/-----T-----T---	
pYK7	*****-----A-/-----T-----T---	
pYK8	*****-----T-/---T-----T-A-----	
pYK9	*****-----TCT»	
	»A--A--T-----GG-----T-----A--A--T---	
K-4 (R)	aaccccaG---/T-----/-----C-CT-C-A-T-----G---AGT-A-C-/A-TA-----T-	
K-2	ctttcaag---G-T-----/-----T-----T-----A-CTA-C-----	
I-09	aggattc-T---T-----T-/---GG-G---T-----*****	
I-21	-----A-----*****	
Consensus	<u>CATGTC</u> <u>TCTATGACATGTGGCTCCAGTGGCAAAATCATTAGAACC</u> <u>ACTCGTAAGAGTGGCAAAATAATTAATTATTC</u>	
pKAY410	-----A-----G---G-----aatatccg	
D16-80	-----G---A---A---A---C---TCGC-///---T---GG//G-----tataaaag	
D11-89	-----C-T-----G-A-C-A---TC-----AAGCC-ctgattcc	
H11-75	-----C-----A-----*****	
pYK1	T-----C-----A-----*****	
pYK2A	--C//-----A-----A-----*****	
pYK2B	-T-A-----T-G-A---A---C-----*****	
pYK3	--A-A-----T-----T-----C-----A-----*****	
pYK4	--C//-----A-----A-----*****	
pYK5	-T-A-----T-----T-G-A---T-----C-----*****	
pYK6	-----A---T---C---A---T---A---T---T-----*****	
pYK7	T-----T-----T---AC---T---A-----*****	
pYK8	-----A-----T-----T---TC---TAT-----*****	
pYK9	-----A-----T-----AT---A---C---TG---T-----*****	
K-4 (R)	T-C-----*****	
II-6	*****-----T-----tgcctgga	
I-9	*****-----T-G-----C-----tthttgga	
D-17	*****-----T-----T-----T---TTgaagtcc	
D-18-2	*****-----T-----T-----C-----/---tgaattgc	

2. Nucleotide sequences of Tnr2 members. The TIR sequences (56 bp) are underlined. - = bases identical to those of consensus sequence of Tnr2, / = bases deleted, * = primer sequences used for PCR. Tandem repeat sequences of 20 bp are double-underlined. Clones pYK2A and pYK4 lack one of the repeating units.

each member had target site duplication (TSD) of 8 bp, confirming that Tnr2 is a transposable element (Fig. 2). PCR using oligonucleotides derived from the Tnr2 flanking sequences as primers revealed that several accessions of AA genome species *O. longistaminata* and *O. glaberrima* also had Tnr2 in the corresponding loci. This indicates that Tnr2 was inserted into each locus before the rice varieties with AA genome had differentiated during evolution. The PCR-amplified fragments,

however, showed length polymorphism caused by deletion within the Tnr2 sequence or in the region flanking Tnr2.

All the Tnr2 members identified in the study are small and are assumed to be a nonautonomous element derived by deletion from an autonomous one that can transpose by itself. Several hundred copies of Tnr2 exist in the rice genome, one of which may correspond to the autonomous Tnr2.

Cited references

- Ohtsubo E, Mochizuki K, Tenzen T, Ohtsubo H. 1993. Gamma Field Symp. 32:71-83.
 Mochizuki K, Ohtsubo H, Hirani H, Sano Y, Ohtsubo E. 1993. Classification and relationship of rice strains with AA genome by identification of transposable elements at nine loci. Jpn. J. Genet. 68:205-217. ■

Breeding methods

New cytoplasmic male sterile lines developed in Andhra Pradesh, India

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Successful use of hybrid vigor in rice largely depends on availability of local cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) and restorer lines. In India, many IRRI-bred CMS lines from the wild abortive (WA) source are being used to develop rice hybrids, which could lead to genetic vulnerability. Use of local CMS lines will help to alleviate this problem and to develop adaptable, heterotic hybrids. We therefore screened several hundred elite genotypes with diverse genetic backgrounds for their maintaining ability at ARS, Maruteru, India.

Two effective maintainers for the WA cytoplasmic source and one effective maintainer for the ARC cytoplasmic source were identified and successfully converted into local CMS lines through backcrossing. Lines with complete pollen sterility identified from BC₆ generation were

designated as APMS1 A (IR54755 A/WGL 3010-407 - ARC source), APMS2 A (V20 A/WGL 3010-407 - WA source) and APMS5A (IR58025 A/MTU4870 - WA source) during 1994-95. These lines, along with IRRI-bred CMS line IR58025 A, were evaluated for their agronomic and floral traits and natural outcrossing potential. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with five replications during the 1995 wet season. Plants were raised at 20 × 20-cm spacing in a 4-m² plot. Five plants from the central row in each replication were observed. To study their natural outcrossing potential, the CMS lines were planted adjacent to the corresponding maintainer lines. Good flowering synchrony was achieved. Seed set was attained without resorting to any supplementary pollination techniques.

Data on six characters were statistically analyzed. The four CMS lines significantly differed in agronomic and floral traits, except for productive tillers plant⁻¹ (see table).

Early-duration (110-115 d) APMS1 A (ARC) and APMS2 A (WA) possess field resistance to gall midge and bacterial leaf

blight (BLB). Their anthers are white and shivered with moderately well-exserted stigmas. These lines may be extremely valuable in developing early to super-early rice hybrids adaptable to different cropping systems.

Long-duration (147 d) APMS5 A has sturdy culms and possesses resistance to brown planthopper, BLB, and rice tungro virus. Spikelet opening angle, stigma exertion, and natural outcrossing potential are comparable with those of popular CMS line IR58025A. APMS5 A is the first long-duration CMS line with desirable floral and agronomic traits developed in India. This line will be useful in developing long-duration rice hybrids suitable for wet-season cultivation in coastal Andhra Pradesh.

We used the three CMS lines for testcrossing with several elite lines, and effective restorers and maintainer were identified. The three CMS lines are potential female parents for developing heterotic rice hybrids adapted to different ecological conditions, including coastal regions of Andhra Pradesh, India.

Agronomic and floral traits of new CMS lines in rice.

CMS line	Days to 50% flowering	Plant height (cm)	Productive tillers/plant (no.)	Duration of spikelet opening (min)	Angle of spikelet opening (°)	Seed set on natural outcrossing (%)	Pollen sterility (%)	Stigma exertion	Anther characteristic
APMS1 A	78.0	86.3	10.3	192.5	26.8	10.0	100	Moderately well exerted	White and shriveled
APMS2 A	80.0	87.5	10.1	183.5	27.0	10.8	100	Moderately well exerted	White and shriveled
APMS5 A	116.7	115.5	9.8	194.0	31.0	12.1	100	Well exerted	White and shriveled
IR58025 A	90.5	90.8	10.1	222.5	30.0	12.6	100	Well exerted	White and shriveled
SEM	0.57	0.63	0.23	4.36	0.21	0.3	-	-	-
CD (0.05)	1.75	1.94	ns	13.39	0.63	0.93	-	-	-
CV (%)	1.40	1.30	5.00	4.90	1.60	6.00	-	-	-